

Synthesis of [10-Substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetyl-3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles/pyrazolones and 5-[10-Substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones

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A large number of indole derivatives linked to various heterocyclic systems¹, carbolines² and pyrazole derivatives³ are known to possess various biological activities. Recently, we have reported a new method for the synthesis of indolo[3,2-*c*]isoquinolin-5-ones/thione and their reactions⁴. We report here the synthesis of some 10-substituted-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolines linked to 3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles, -pyrazolones and 1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones via acetyl and methyl groups respectively. Also, we report here the synthesis of 5-oxo-1,2,4-triazolo[5,6-*c*]-7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolines, which is a new heterocyclic system.

Results and Discussion

The starting compounds, 10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-ones (**1a-c**) were prepared according to the literature methods⁵. These compounds (**1a-c**) were reacted with ethyl chloroacetate to give ethyl [10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetates (**2a-c**). Compounds **2a-c** were reacted with hydrazine hydrate to yield [10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl] acetylhydrazides (**3a-c**). The hydrazides (**3a-c**) were condensed with benzoyl acetone, dibenzoyl methane and ethyl acetoacetate to get the corresponding 1-[10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetyl-3-phenyl-5-methyl-pyrazoles (**4a-c**), -3,5-diphenylpyrazoles (**5a-c**) and -3-methylpyrazol-5-ones (**6a-c**) (Scheme 1). The *ir*^{4,7} and ¹H nmr spectra are in conformity with their structures.

Scheme 1

The hydrazides (**3a-c**) reacted with CS₂ in methanolic KOH to yield 5-[10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thiones (**7a-c**).

Compounds **1a-c** when reacted with ethyl

chloroformate under the conditions described for **2a-c**, yielded the ethyl [10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]carboxylates (**8a-c**). The esters (**8a-c**) were reacted with hydrazine hydrate to get the corresponding [10-substituted-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]hydrazides (**9a-c**). The hydrazides (**9a-c**) were subjected to cyclodehydration in ammonium acetate and acetic acid to yield the 5-oxo-1,2,4-triazolo[5,6-*c*]-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolines (**10a-c**).

Biological activities :

Antibacterial activity : The compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *P. vulgaris*, *P. aeruginosa* and *S. citreus* by cup-plate method, using gentamycin (20 µg/0.1 ml) as standard. The compounds were tested at concentration of 50 µg in DMF. Compounds **4a**, **4b**, **5c**, **8b** and **9c** exhibited a high degree of inhibition against *E. coli*, **4b**, **6b**, **6c** and **10b** were highly active against *P. vulgaris*, **3c**, **4b**, **5a**, **7b** and **10c** inhibited the growth of *P. aeruginosa*, whereas compounds **5b**, **5c**, **7b** and **9c** exhibited maximum inhibition against *S. citreus*. Rest of the compounds showed moderate or less activity against all the four organisms. None of the compounds showed any significant activity as compared to that of the standard.

Antifungal activity : The compounds were tested for their antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* using griseofulvin (40 µg/0.1 ml) as standard at concentration of 75 µg in DMF. Compounds **3b**, **7a** and **9a** exhibited high degree of inhibition against *C. albicans*, whereas **4b**, **6a**, **7b** and **9c** showed highest activity against *A. niger*. The other compounds showed moderate or less activity against both the organisms. None of the compounds showed any significant activity as compared to the standard.

Anthelmintic activity : The anthelmintic activity of all compounds was carried out against *Pheretima postuma* by following the reported procedure⁶ using mebendazole suspension (2 mg/ml) as standard. Compound **4b**, **6a**, **9a** and **10c** were found active at a concentration of 10 mg/ml, whereas other compounds did not show significant activity. None of the compounds showed any significant activity compared to the standard.

Experimental

All m.ps. were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 297 spectropotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian EM-60 (60 MHz) and EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as the internal standard.

Ethyl [10-methoxy-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetate (2a) : A mixture of **1a** (0.01 mol), ethyl chloroacetate (0.01 mol) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.02 mol) in dry acetone was refluxed on steam-bath for 8 h. The inorganic solids were filtered while hot, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was triturated with water to remove potassium carbonate, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (50%), m.p. 215–16°; ν_{\max} 3 200 (NH), 1 740 (C=O) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O)^{4,7}; δ 6.8-8.2 (8H, m, 7-ArH + indole NH), 4.1 (4H, q, N-CH₂ and O=COCH₂), 3.2 (3H, s, O-CH₃) and 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃); *m/z* 350 (*M*⁺, 100%) and 263 (10%) 232 (6%) are the fragments observed by the consecutive loss of CH₂COOC₂H₅, OCH₃ fragments respectively, from the molecular ion (*M*⁺). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **2b** (52%), m.p. 241–42°; **2c** (62%), 175–76°.

10-Methoxy-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetylhydrazide (3a) : To a suspension of **2a** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), hydrazine hydrate (5 ml; 99–100%) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h. After cooling the resulting crystalline product was washed with alcohol, dried and crystallised from alcohol, (72%), m.p. > 300°, ν_{\max} 3 300 (indole NH), 3 200, 3 150 (NH/NH₂), 1 660 (C=O) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=O)^{4,7}, *m/z* 336 (*M*⁺, 69%), and 305 (83%), 277 (47%) and 249 (69%) are due to the sequential loss of NHNH₂, CO and CO fragments from the molecular ion (*M*⁺) respectively. Other compounds were prepared similarly: **3b** (76%), m.p. >300°; **3c** (75%), > 300.

1-[10-Methoxy-6*H*,7*H*-indolo[2,3-*c*]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetyl-3,5-disubstituted-pyrazoles (4a and 5a) : A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane (0.01 mol) was refluxed in methanol (10 ml) containing 4-5 drops of con-

concentrated HCl for 4 h on a steam-bath. It was then concentrated and cooled to room temperature. The separated yellow solid was washed with little methanol, dried and crystallised from alcohol : **4a** (69%), m.p. 229–30°; ν_{\max} 3 300 (NH), 1 750 (C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O)^{4,7}; δ 7.0–8.3 (13H, m, 12-ArH + indole NH), 6.33 (1H, s, =CH), 4.1 (2H, s, CH₂C=O), 3.60 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **4b** (68%), m.p. 260–62°; **4c** (74%), 250–51°; **5a** (72%), > 300°; **5b** (75%), m.p. 279–81°; **5c** (74%), 255–57°.

1-[10-Methoxy-6H,7H-indolo[2,3-c]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]acetyl-3-methylpyrazol-5-ones (6a) : It was prepared by following the procedure described for **4a** and **5a** from of **3a** and ethyl acetoacetate, and product was crystallised from alcohol, (70%), m.p. > 300°; ν_{\max} 3 400 (NH), 1740 (C=O), 1 720 (C=O) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=O). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **6b** (73%), m.p. 245–46°; **6c** (71%), 261–62°.

5-[10-Methoxy-6H,7H-indolo[2,3-c]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-thione (7a) : A mixture of **3a** (0.005 mol), KOH (0.005 mol) and CS₂ (5 ml) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath until the evolution of H₂S ceased (45–48 h). The solvent was then evaporated and the residue dissolved in ice-water. The resulting clear solution was filtered and the filtrate was acidified with dilute HCl. The separated solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (56%), m.p. 251–52°; ν_{\max} 3 250 (NH), 3 200 (NH), 1 630 (C=O) and 1 060 cm^{-1} (C=S). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **7b** (52%), m.p. 182–83°; **7c** (58%), 274–75°.

Ethyl [10-methoxy-6H,7H-indolo[2,3-c]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]carboxylate (8a) : It was prepared according to the procedure described for **2a**, reacting **1a** and ethyl chloroformate and the product was crystallised from ethanol, (52%), m.p. 157–58°; ν_{\max} 3 350 (NH), 1 760 (C=O) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O)⁸; m/z 336 (M^+ , 44%), and 264 (42%) and 221 (17%) are due to the loss of COOC₂H₄ and NHCO fragments respectively, from the molecular ion (M^+). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **8b** (58%), m.p. 126°; **8c** (58%), 202–03°.

[10-Methoxy-6H,7H-indolo[2,3-c]isoquinolin-5-one-6-yl]hydrazide (9a) : It was obtained following the procedure described for **3a** by reacting **8a** with hydrazine hydrate. The product was crystallised from alcohol, (78%), m.p. > 300°; ν_{\max} 3 350 (indole NH), 3 300, 3 250 (NH/NH₂), 1 620 (C=O) and 1 610 cm^{-1} (C=O)⁸; m/z 322 (M^+ , 30%), 263 (56%), 235 (20%), 204 (34%), and 177 (16%) are due to the sequential loss of CONHNH₂, CO, OCH₃ and HCN from the molecular ion (M^+). Other compounds were prepared similarly : **9b** (70%), m.p. > 300°; **9c** (76%), > 300°.

9-Bromo-5-oxo-1,2,4-triazolo[5,6-c]-7H-indolo[2,3-c]isoquinolines (10c) : A mixture of **9c** (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 4 h when yellow colour of the reaction mixture changed to dark brown. It was then cooled, poured onto crushed ice and neutralised with ammonia. The solid obtained was dried and crystallised from ethanol, (73%), m.p. > 300°, ν_{\max} 3 400 (indole NH), 3 350 (NH), 1 610 (C=O), 1 580 cm^{-1} (C=N); **10c**, m/z 354, 352 (M^+ , 100%), and 311, 309 (35%) and 230 (77%) are due to the loss of NHCO and Br from the molecular ion (M^+) respectively. Other compounds were prepared similarly : **10b** (70%), m.p. > 300° ; **10a** (65%), > 300°.

The rest of the compounds reported here were prepared following the procedure described for a representative compound in each of the series.

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References

- 1 S P. HIREMATH, A C BAJJI and J S BIRADAR, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1989, **28**, 824; S P HIREMATH, P S BADAMI and M G PUROHIT, *Indian J Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 437, S. P HIREMATH, K M K SWAMY and B H M. MRUTHYUNJAYASWAMY, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 83; S P. HIREMATH, D M HIREMATH and M G. PUROHIT, *Indian J Chem., Sect. B.*, 1984, **23**, 930
- 2 V C. SAXENA, S K. BAPAT and S. N DHAWAN *Jpn J Pharmacol.*, 1969, **19**, 477. (*Chem Abstr.*, 1970, **72**, 65152); A. COHAN and C J CATTANACH, US Pat 3 316 271/1967 (*Chem Abstr.*, 1967, **67**, 21900). D. L GARMAISE, G V. PARK and N. P PLOTNICKOFF, US Pat

- 3 705 902/ 1971 (*Chan. Abstr.*, 1973, 78, 72103); K. ISHIZUMI and J. KATSUBE, Ger. Pat. 2 826 269/1979 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1980, 92, 128891).
3. R. B. PATHAK and S. C. BAHTEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1108; T. TRIKURA, Jap. Pat. 7 570 367/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, 84, 59445), A. J. EID, M. A. KIRA and H. N. FAHMY, *J. Pharm. Belg.*, 1978, 33, 303 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, 90, 152073).
 4. S. P. HIREMATH, A. R. SAUNDANE and B. H. M. MRUTHYUNJAYASWAMY, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1993, 30, 603.
 5. S. P. HIREMATH, P. S. BADAMI and M. G. PUROHIT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, 24, 1235.
 6. K. N. GIAND, R. N. DAR, B. M. CHOPRA and R. N. KAUL, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1965, 27, 141.
 7. M. Z. A. BADR, S. A. MAHCOUB, F. F. ABDEL-LATIF, A. M. FAHMY and O. S. MOUSTAFA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, 67, 216.
 8. M. B. HOGALE, A. C. UTHALE and B. P. NIKAM, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, 30, 717.